

Review

Life after Trastuzumab: Neu Strategies for HER2-positive Breast Cancer

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Abstract

The importance of *neu* in breast cancer provided the rationale and impetus for developing agents that targeted the receptor. Proof of therapeutic principle was subsequently established with trastuzumab. Although not minimal, the improved clinical outcomes with the antibody were somewhat counterbalanced by disease relapses which occurred in advanced and adjuvant therapy settings. What this observation suggests is that while tumor response may be due principally to uncoupling the link between cell surface message reception and nuclear gene expression, disease progression appears to involve a re-programmable cellular mainframe that enables alternative tumor growth and survival pathways to become operational. The goal of this paper is to meld biological and therapeutic concepts that have resulted in further advances in the treatment of *neu*-amplified breast cancers.

Keywords

ado-trastuzumab emtansine, afatinib, ErbB, HER2, lapatinib, neratinib, neu, pertuzumab, receptor tyrosine kinase

Neu profile

One of the most significant achievements in breast cancer over the past 30 years was the discovery of *neu*, the proto-oncogene which encodes a 185 kDa transmembrane receptor (p185^{HER2/neu})[1]. Another revelation related to this finding was the relationship between *neu* and a gene found in the avian erythroblastosis virus (*v-ErbB*) that encoded epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR)[2]. The close association of the two genes is further supported by the amino acid homology that exists between their respective encoded onco-proteins. Moreover, this is how HER (Human EGFR-Related) 2/*neu* derives its name; and the manner in which the three other members of the ErbB receptor family, HER1 (EGFR), HER3, and HER4, are identified.

Structurally, all HER-family members are configured with an extracellular receptor-binding portion and an intracellular catalytic kinase domain that is connected by a short membrane-spanning region (Figure 1)[3]. Ligand binding, which promotes receptor dimerization, was initially considered the primal event which activated the internal signal transduction pathway. However, newer data suggest that receptor conformation, rather than phosphorylation, is the principal determinant of kinase activation[4]. Nonetheless, the ultimate cellular response depends on a complex process involving recruitment and activation of additional protein kinases located downstream of the receptor (Figure 2).

While receptors are essential for regulating normal tissue development, they could also be detrimental to the cell. This biological paradox is

certainly applicable to the effects mediated through HER2 on breast tissue. Whereas normal signaling through the receptor promotes lobuloalveolar differentiation and lactation, overexpression of HER2 on breast tumor cells characterizes a molecular subtype of breast cancer. However, it should be emphasized that HER2 expression alone neither identifies nor correlates with this unique tumor phenotype. Instead, gene amplification and/or receptor overexpression confers the only accepted designation of HER2-positivity, a diagnostic subtype of approximately 20% of all breast cancers [5-7]. An extension of the importance of this genetic and molecular abnormality has been validated in four ways. First, association between receptor over-expression, adverse tumor features, and relatively poorer prognosis; second, confirmation that amplified HER2/*neu* has both predictive and prognostic value [8]; third, identification of the receptor provided a stimulus for developing agents that specifically targeted *neu* [9]; and fourth, realization that disease relapse occurs in patients treated with trastuzumab in both metastatic and adjuvant therapy settings. All of these observations, especially the latter, emphasized the need for alternative treatment options for patients with trastuzumab intolerance or disease progressing on, or refractory to, trastuzumab. This concern is extremely important because of the finding that HER2 remains a viable target despite the apparent loss of antibody activity [10]. Indeed, continuation of trastuzumab with different chemotherapy in patients whose breast cancers progressed during treatment resulted in longer median time to progression (TTP) and higher overall response rates

Figure 1 Structure and conformation ErbB family members. Each member has a ligand-binding extracellular, a trans-membrane, and an intracellular kinase domain. Ligand-binding is localized to a site between CR1 and CR2. In contrast to the “closed” position of HER2, the “open” conformer exhibited by HER1, HER3, and HER4 appears to allow ligand access. Two items of note: 1) no endogenous ligand for HER2 has been identified and 2) the defective or deficient kinase activity of HER3.

(ORR) compared to chemotherapy alone. These outcomes suggest that resistance to trastuzumab-containing chemotherapy regimens is not necessarily due to HER2-mediated mechanisms alone.

The primary purpose of this paper was to demonstrate how increased understanding of the receptor provided insight regarding potential resistance mechanisms, which could then be translated into developing additional pharmacologic strategies for HER2-amplified (or overexpressed) breast cancer. As such, a comprehensive discussion of novel therapeutic agents that followed trastuzumab was undertaken. Where appropriate, additional information, some old but of enduring scientific value, has also been included in order to elucidate the impact other intracellular components may have on the neu-signaling pathway. Lastly, the paper highlights a number of uncertainties that persist despite the clinical progress made in treating this particular subtype of breast cancer.

Neu dimers and resistance

Another aspect of the landmark achievement associated with trastuzumab is the sobering reality that nearly all HER2/neu-positive metastatic breast cancers progress, usually within 12 months after initially responding to the antibody [11]. Even when used in the adjuvant setting, relapses have occurred following trastuzumab therapy [12,13]. The inability to explain why initial HER2-directed therapy becomes ineffective has made it difficult to develop and apply strategies that overcome, prevent, or delay the development of resistance. Elucidating the mechanistic basis of neu-resistance is speculative at best and made even more difficult because the receptor is, arguably, the most enigmatic member of the ErbB family. Although overexpression

of HER2 results in formation of constitutively active homodimers [14], it is conceivable that the development of resistance is due, in part, to HER2’s dimeric partner (Figure 3) [15]. For example, it has been shown that the dimerization partner and its activating ligand play essential roles in determining not only which receptor sites are phosphorylated, but also which downstream proteins are recruited [16]. Hence, tumorigenic signals emanating from novel heterodimers could have greater mitogenic potential compared to homodimeric HER2 [17,18].

HER1/HER2/neu

The added signaling potency of the HER1/HER2 heterodimer may be one mechanism by which tumors develop resistance to trastuzumab [18]. However, neu may have another means through which the disease is able to “escape” antibody-associated cell death. Molecularly, encoded full-length HER2 (p185^{ErbB2}) undergoes proteolytic cleavage resulting in a deceptively shortened receptor (p95^{ErbB2}) with increased autokinase activity [19]. The truncated receptor is notable in that loss of the drug-binding epitope may contribute to tumor unresponsiveness to trastuzumab [20]. Clinically, elevated serum levels of the dissociated extracellular domain (ECD) have not only been correlated with poorer responses [21], but also appear to be a biologic marker of increased sensitivity to small molecule kinase inhibitors. Collectively, the latter two observations supported the rationale for the development of lapatinib, an agent which can block signaling through formed HER1 and full-length or truncated HER2 heterodimers.

Lapatinib (TykerbTM, GlaxoSMITHKline) is a potent, reversible, small molecule inhibitor of HER1 and HER2 (Figure 3). Structured crystal analysis of the

Figure 2 Targeting the HER2 signaling pathway. HER2 is the preferential partner in four possible dimers. Epidermal growth factor (EGF)-bound HER1 can form heterodimers with HER2. As a result, the MAPK (mitogen-activated protein kinase) pathway can be activated. Ras is engaged following recruitment of Shc and Grb2 (growth-factor receptor bound protein 2). Grb2 forms a complex with son of sevenless (SoS). Downstream of Ras are Raf, MEK (mitogen activated protein kinase kinase), and ERK (extracellular signal-regulated kinase). HER3 preferentially signals through the PI3K (phosphatidylinositol 3 kinase) survival pathway. Akt blocks cell death by inhibiting pro-apoptotic proteins or up-regulating anti-apoptotic proteins. Akt can also promote angiogenesis via mTOR (mammalian target of rapamycin). PTEN (phosphatase and tensin homolog) is a negative regulator of Akt. The monoclonal antibodies bind to a site on the extracellular domain of the receptor. However, pertuzumab appears to bind to a site distinct from trastuzumab and TDM-1. As such, pertuzumab is able to “sterically” hinder HER2 from dimerizing with other HER family members. This property may result in an additive or synergistic effect when pertuzumab is combined with any other HER2-targeted agent.

lapatinib/HER1 complex revealed that lapatinib dissociates much slower from the receptor compared to erlotinib, which correlates with the prolonged time tyrosine phosphorylation is down-regulated in tumor cells [22]. Similar crystallographic and stoichiometric studies of lapatinib’s interaction with HER2 have not been published, though substantial evidence indicate that receptor phosphorylation is similarly depressed [20]. Data from a phase 1 study indicated that HER2-overexpressing breast tumor responses correlated with median daily lapatinib dosages of 1200 mg and C_{min} serum concentration between 0.3 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ - 0.6 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ which, interestingly, corresponded to the inhibitory effect on HER1 and HER2 kinase activity *in-vitro* [23,24].

Lapatinib was the first new drug to demonstrate significant clinical benefits in patients with HER2-positive, advanced breast cancer that had progressed on trastuzumab. The results of a pivotal phase III clinical trial involving women with advanced, HER2-positive, trastuzumab- and chemotherapy-refractory breast cancer, have been published (study details in Table 1) [25]. It should be noted that the study was terminated early when a pre-planned interim analysis performed by an independent data monitoring committee showed a significant benefit for subjects randomized to the lapatinib arm. At

that time, 324 patients had been randomized to capecitabine plus lapatinib ($n=163$) or capecitabine alone ($n=161$). On the basis of 121 events, 49 in the combination and 72 in the monotherapy groups, median TTP was nearly twice as long among patients receiving the lapatinib-containing regimen compared to capecitabine alone, 8.4 months and 4.4 months, respectively, $p<0.001$. Progression-free survival (PFS) was also improved in the group treated with the two agents (HR, 0.47; 95% CI, 0.33 to 0.67; $p<0.001$). Equally noteworthy were observations related to brain metastasis. An update of the data continued to show superior efficacy of the lapatinib-containing arm compared to capecitabine alone [26]. Two salient issues add credence to the results of this clinical trial. First, despite an earlier study [23] of lapatinib which suggested that clinical responses may be higher in breast tumors that co-expressed HER1, the absence of HER1 expression was not an exclusion criterion. Second, the fact that nearly two-thirds of the patients received trastuzumab within the previous eight weeks led to the speculation that the positive outcomes could have been partly related to the combined effect between residual amounts of trastuzumab and recently administered lapatinib [27]. However, analysis of data in women who received lapatinib and prior trastuzumab (<8

wk versus >8 wk) indicated that the contribution of residual trastuzumab appeared to be minimal [28].

Figure 3 HER2 dimers. Four different dimers can be formed involving HER2. Intuitively, tumor over-expression of HER2 would bias the formation of neu homodimers. Despite the absence of native ligands, HER2 homodimers are constitutively activated. Equally important, partners including HER1 and HER3 result in receptor-mediated transactivation of HER2. The activity of the HER2/HER4 heterodimer is not well described.

Outcomes regarding CNS metastasis deserve further comment. A small, but significant, number of patients (approximately 15%) with advanced breast cancer develop symptomatic brain metastasis [29]. The observation that CNS disease as the site of first relapse occurs more frequently in a subset of patients treated with trastuzumab compared to patients who receive standard chemotherapy alone appears to be a troubling anomaly [30,31]. Attempts to reconcile this finding include two plausible reasons. One relates to the demonstrated effectiveness of trastuzumab in that prolongation of survival may also translate to an increased risk of eventually developing cerebral metastasis. Another consideration is the blood-brain barrier may create a sanctuary for tumor cells by restricting or limiting penetration of the large molecular-sized antibody. Hence, it is conceivable that one of the advantages of small molecule inhibitors such as lapatinib may relate to its ability to cross into the CNS and lower the frequency of, or even treat, brain metastasis. Although modest, clinical evidence of the latter effect has also been published [32].

Few reports of lapatinib as first-line therapy of HER-2 positive breast cancer have been published. One, a randomized, open-label study compared the efficacy and safety of two different lapatinib dosages and administration schedules, 1,500 mg once daily and 500 mg twice daily [33]. The ORR was 24% in the intent-to-treat population consisting of 138 subjects; an additional 7% of the patients had stable disease. The median time to response was approximately 8

weeks. The most common lapatinib-related adverse events (AEs), primarily grade 1 or 2) were diarrhea, rash, pruritus, and nausea. There were no apparent differences in either clinical activity or the AE profile between the two arms.

At least three phase III studies of lapatinib in combination with a taxane are ongoing. However, one of the most intriguing clinical trials in progress compares an aromatase inhibitor with or without lapatinib in women with estrogen receptor (ER)-positive tumors regardless of HER2 status [34]. The rationale for this clinical trial was based on laboratory findings that bi-directional crosstalk between ER and HER2 could enhance tumor cell proliferation and cell survival [35]. In this study, 1171 postmenopausal women with ER-positive metastatic breast cancer were randomly assigned to receive daily doses of letrozole (2.5 mg orally) plus lapatinib (1,500 mg orally) or letrozole (same dose) and placebo. Only 19% (n=219) of the enrolled subjects were also HER2-positive. The primary end point was PFS. Among the cohort of women who had hormone and HER2 receptor-positive tumors, the combination of agents was associated with a 29% reduction in risk of disease progression compared to those receiving the placebo, (HR, 0.71; 95% CI, 0.53 to 0.96; $p=0.019$); median PFS was 8.2 vs 3 months, respectively. Clinical benefit rate (CBR = complete response [CR] + partial response [PR] + stable disease [SD] >6 months) was also significantly greater for lapatinib/letrozole versus letrozole/placebo (48% vs 29%, respectively; $p=0.003$). Arguably, the relative

importance of the two receptors relates not only to the superior disease-related outcomes achieved with combination therapy (which could have been anticipated) but also their presence provided biological targeted-proof of principle.

Design	Key eligibility criteria	Treatment schema	End points
Phase 3 open-label study comparing lapatinib + capecitabine against capecitabine alone [Ref 25]	HER2-positive locally-advanced or metastatic breast cancer progressing on prior anthracycline, taxane, and trastuzumab therapy. HER2 status confirmed by IHC 3+ or 2+ by IHC and gene amplification by FISH.	Lapatinib 1250 mg q AM continuously + capecitabine 1000 mg/m ² BID days 1-14 of 21 day cycle versus capecitabine 1250 mg/m ² BID days 1-14 of 21 day cycle.	¹ ° TTP ² ° PFS, OS, ORR, CBR, and safety
Phase 3 randomized, multicenter, open-label study designed to compare the efficacy and safety of lapatinib + trastuzumab against lapatinib alone [Ref 36]	HER2-positive, metastatic breast cancer progressing on most recent (either adjuvant or metastatic setting) treatment (must have received anthracycline- and taxane-based) regimens. HER2 status confirmed by gene amplification (FISH) or 3+ IHC overexpression.	Random assignment (1:1) to lapatinib 1,000 mg QD in combination with trastuzumab 4 mg/kg load followed by 2 mg/kg weekly versus lapatinib 1,500 mg daily. Subjects with disease progression after at least 4 weeks of treatment with lapatinib alone permitted to crossover.	¹ ° PFS (based on investigator assessments according to RECIST; supporting data provided by independent review) ² ° ORR, CBR, OS, QOL, and safety
Phase 1/2, open-label study. Phase 1 = dose-escalation in patients with advanced solid tumors to determine the maximum tolerated dose (MTD). After determining the MTD, phase 2 evaluated the efficacy and safety of neratinib plus vinorelbine in patients with HER2-positive metastatic breast cancer. One interim analysis planned after ~20 assessable subjects with no prior lapatinib exposure were enrolled; if five or fewer responders were observed, enrollment stoppage was considered. [Ref 46]	Metastatic HER2-positive breast cancer by FISH (for which vinorelbine + neratinib was a reasonable option). At least one prior treatment for metastatic disease or disease relapse during adjuvant therapy. ECOG PS to 2 Exclusion criteria included symptomatic CNS disease; >2 prior chemotherapy treatment regimens for metastatic disease; prior treatment with vinorelbine for metastatic disease or with any HER2-targeted agents except trastuzumab.	Neratinib 240 mg QD and vinorelbine 25 mg/m ² q weekly.	¹ ° ORR ² ° PFS, CBR, duration of response (DOR)
Phase 2, open-label multi-site, two cohort study. Cohort A (prior treatment with trastuzumab defined by progression after at least 6 weeks of trastuzumab in the metastatic or locally advanced setting or progression on or after trastuzumab-containing adjuvant therapy) and Cohort B (patients with no prior treatment with trastuzumab). [Ref 47]	HER2-positive (independently assessed <i>ERBB2</i> by FISH); stage III, IBC, or IV breast cancer not curable with available therapy. ECOG PS to 2; <4 prior chemotherapy regimens including anthracyclines. Patients with active CNS disease were excluded.	Neratinib 240 mg QD.	¹ ° 16 week PFS ² ° ORR, CBR, DOR, safety
Phase 3 randomized, double-blind, placebo controlled study comparing trastuzumab and docetaxel + pertuzumab. [Ref 59]	HER2-positive (3+ IHC or FISH), locally recurrent or metastatic breast cancer. No prior therapy for metastatic disease. ECOG PS 0 or 1; prior adjuvant chemotherapy +/- trastuzumab completed >12 months prior to diagnosis of metastatic breast cancer.	Random assignment (1:1 ratio) to trastuzumab 8 mg/kg load then 6 mg/kg q 3 weeks + docetaxel 75 mg/m ² q 3 weeks + pertuzumab 840 mg load then 420 mg q 3 weeks versus same doses of trastuzumab + docetaxel as above + placebo.	¹ ° PFS ² ° OS, ORR, safety
Phase 3 randomized, open-label, international trial designed to compare the efficacy/safety of T-DM1 against the combination of lapatinib + capecitabine. [Ref 67]	Unresectable, locally advanced or metastatic HER2-positive (IHC 3+ or FISH) breast cancer previously treated with taxane and trastuzumab; LVEF fraction of >50% ECHO or MUGA; ECOG PS 0 or 1 Exclusion: prior treatment with T-DM1, lapatinib, or capecitabine; peripheral neuropathy of grade >3; symptomatic CNS metastases; or treatment for these metastases within 2 months before randomization; history of symptomatic CHF or serious cardiac arrhythmia requiring treatment; and a history of MI.	Random assignment (1:1 ratio) to T-DM1 3.6 mg/kg Q 21 days. Dose reductions due to toxicity to 3.0 mg/kg then to 2.4 mg/kg were allowed per protocol or lapatinib 1250 mg QD + capecitabine 1000 mg/m ² (maximum daily dose) Q12 h days 1-14 each 21-day cycle.	¹ ° PFS (assessed by independent review), OS, and safety. ² ° PFS (investigator-assessed), ORR, DOR, and time to symptom progression based on Trial Outcome Index of the patient-reported Functional Assessment of Cancer Therapy-Breast (FACT-B TD)

Table 1 Key clinical trials conducted with new anti-HER2 agents

Perhaps, and not without regard for HER1, targeting the intracellular HER2 kinase domain has been an effective therapeutic option for patients with disease progressing on trastuzumab [25]. More intriguing, however, is whether trastuzumab and lapatinib, each poised at two different HER2 domains, are better than either agent given alone. This is an important question as mechanistic differences between the two classes of drugs could have significant clinical implications. Therefore, an opportunity exists to assess whether targeting HER2 from the “outside” and “inside” concurrently has additive or perhaps even synergistic activity in patients with HER2-overexpressing breast cancers. One small study was designed to test this hypothesis (study details in Table 1) [36]. Two hundred ninety-six subjects with HER2-positive metastatic breast cancer

with disease progression on prior trastuzumab therapy were randomly assigned to receive either lapatinib alone or in combination with trastuzumab. The primary end point was PFS; secondary end points included CBR and overall survival (OS). Results indicated a superior PFS with the combination of lapatinib and trastuzumab compared to lapatinib alone, (HR, 0.73; 95% CI, 0.57 to 0.93; $p=0.008$); CBR 24.7% and 12.4% in the same two arms, respectively; $p=0.01$; and a trend towards improved OS with combination therapy. The incidence of diarrhea, one of the most frequent AEs, was higher in the combination arm ($p=0.03$). Symptomatic and asymptomatic cardiac events with the combination were 2% and 3.4%, respectively; the incidence of similar cardiac events with lapatinib alone was 0.7% and 1.4%.

A common practice in oncology is to conduct clinical trials of an agent with demonstrated activity in the advanced-disease setting in patients with early-stage disease. Because the primary endpoint or goal of therapy in the latter is cure, an important consideration is the potential impact of a drug’s adverse effect profile. In contrast to most adjuvant therapy which is usually of short duration (i.e., <6 months), standard adjuvant anti-HER2 therapy is currently set at 12 months. Thus, the development of toxicities such as congestive heart failure becomes an important consideration. There is some evidence that lapatinib alone does not confer a high risk of developing heart failure. Analysis of cardiac function in a large cohort of patients ($n=3,558$) treated with lapatinib either as monotherapy or in combination with cytotoxic agents indicated an incidence of 1.6% with confirmed decreases in left ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF); only seven of the 58 patients (0.2%) were symptomatic.[37]However, the answer related to this issue is not absolute as the possibility of selection bias and the relatively short observation period could impact future outcomes. While cardiac monitoring is mandatory in patients receiving lapatinib, it is also important to note that asymptomatic decreases in LVEF have been reported to be two-to-four-fold higher than in the general population [38].

A phase III clinical trial called Adjuvant Lapatinib and/or Trastuzumab Treatment Optimization (ALTO) was conducted to evaluate the comparative effectiveness of lapatinib against trastuzumab in patients with HER2-overexpressing early breast cancer [39]. In order to meet the primary endpoints of OS and TTP, investigators planned to enroll approximately 8,400 women who would be followed for 10 years after randomization. Essentially non-inferiority in design, the trial investigated four treatment arms following surgery: 1) trastuzumab for one year, 2) lapatinib for one year, 3) both agents for one year, or 4) trastuzumab for 12 weeks, followed sequentially by a six week therapy-free period, then lapatinib for 34 weeks. Begun in June of 2007, the accrual goal was met in July 2011. Because early analysis of data indicated that lapatinib alone was not expected to meet the criterion of non-

inferiority, arm 2 of the study was discontinued. As such, trastuzumab remains the only HER2-targeted agent approved for use in the adjuvant setting.

A companion study known as NeoALTTO was conducted between January 2008 and May 2010 to test the hypothesis that same two anti-HER2 agents given concurrently would be better than single-agent therapy [40]. This randomized, open-label, phase 3 study involved women with HER2-positive primary breast cancer with tumors exceeding 2 cm. Four-hundred fifty-five subjects were randomly assigned to monotherapy lapatinib or trastuzumab, or the combination. Neoadjuvant anti-HER2 therapy was given for the first 6 weeks; weekly paclitaxel was then added to the regimen for an additional 12 weeks followed by definitive surgery. After surgery, patients received adjuvant chemotherapy followed by the same targeted therapy as in the neoadjuvant phase to complete one year of treatment. The primary endpoint was the rate of pathological complete response (pCR). The results indicated that the pCR rate was significantly higher in the group treated with both agents (51.3%; 95% CI, 43.1 to 59.5) than the groups given trastuzumab alone (29.5%; 95% CI, 22.4 to 37.5) or lapatinib alone (24.7%; 95% CI, 18.1 to 32.3); $p=0.0001$. No major cardiac events were observed. Again, the frequency of grade 3 diarrhea was higher with lapatinib, either alone (23.4%) or in combination with trastuzumab (21.1%) compared to trastuzumab alone (2.0%).

The approval of lapatinib for the treatment of trastuzumab-resistant advanced breast cancer can be viewed as a substantial therapeutic advance. In some respects, results of the randomized phase III study strengthen this perception as lapatinib in combination with capecitabine significantly reduced the risk of disease progression and improved the overall response rates. Furthermore, the addition of lapatinib to chemotherapy was not related to increases in rates of adverse events or withdrawal due to serious toxicity. An alternative perspective is that lapatinib may not be superior to the humanized antibody as results of the ALTTO trial indicate. However, these observations should not be inferred that there is little or nothing to be gained by inhibiting HER1 in breast cancer. Although the somewhat disappointing outcomes may be related to antagonistic pharmacologic and/or molecular mechanisms, the findings indirectly raise the question of how much of lapatinib's effect can be attributed to inhibition of HER1.

Neratinib

Not yet approved by the FDA, this tyrosine kinase inhibitor has a broader spectrum of inhibitory activity than lapatinib. When tested, neratinib inhibited HER1 and HER2, and to a lesser extent, vascular endothelial growth factor receptor (VEGFR)-2 and Src [41]. What likely contributes to the greater potency of this small molecule compared to lapatinib is a chemical modification known as the Michael addition, which results in irreversible binding and thus, inhibition of the targeted receptors [42,43]. Preclinical data also suggest that neratinib can overcome resistance

that HER1 acquires after initially responding to either gefitinib or erlotinib treatment [43]. Results of a phase I trial involving patients with metastatic HER1- or HER2-positive cancers that had failed standard therapy were recently published [44]. Dose-limiting diarrhea occurred at 400 mg given once daily; constitutional symptoms such as fatigue and asthenia were also observed frequently. Notably, partial responses (PRs) were achieved in 8 (32%) of 25 evaluable patients with breast cancer.

Preliminary results of efficacy and safety have also been reported from three clinical trials. The first, a two part phase 1/2 open-label study was conducted to evaluate the combination of neratinib and paclitaxel [45]. Part 1 was designed to assess the safety of neratinib at 160 mg or 240 mg daily when given with weekly paclitaxel in patients with advanced solid tumors. The second part of the study evaluated the ORR of the combination at their maximum tolerated doses in patients with HER2-positive metastatic breast cancer. Of the 99 evaluable patients enrolled in part 2 (and based on investigator assessment), 68 (69%) patients achieved an objective response (5 CRs; 63 PRs). Interestingly, the percent of patients achieving either a CR or PR was nearly identical regardless if it was given as first-line or second-line therapy. Thirteen additional patients had SD >24 weeks as their best outcome; only six patients developed progressive disease (PD). Of the 28 patients who received prior trastuzumab and the 14 patients previously treated with lapatinib, 18 (64%) and 10 (71%), respectively, achieved an objective response. Median PFS for all patients with HER2-positive breast cancer was approximately 52 weeks (95% CI, 47.7 to NE). The confidence interval can be interpreted to mean that while the lower boundary represents a median PFS of 47.7 weeks, the upper boundary is non-estimable (i.e., NE). An explanation for the NE status is most likely related to disease status as many of the patients had not yet "progressed".

The results of a second phase 1/2 trial have recently been reported (study details in Table 1) [46]. Similar in design to the previous study neratinib, was given concomitantly with vinorelbine to 34 patients with advanced HER2-positive breast cancer, all of who received prior trastuzumab and taxane therapy. Twenty-two patients were also treated previously with an anthracycline. At the time of their report, 18 patients were evaluable, 4 of who received prior trastuzumab and lapatinib. Although there were no CRs, seven (68%) patients achieved at least a PR; SD >24 weeks was observed in three additional patients. The third study included 136 women with locally advanced (stage IIIB and IIIC) and metastatic HER2-positive breast cancer (study details in Table 1) [47]. This phase 2 study was designed to evaluate neratinib as a single agent. The study's primary end point was 16-week PFS rate; secondary end points included safety, ORR, and CBR. Based on prior trastuzumab therapy, two study arms were created; arm A included patients who received at least 6 weeks of prior trastuzumab therapy while arm B

consisted of patients who never received treatment with any HER2-targeted agent. Of the 136 patients, 127 were included in the efficacy analysis; 63 in arm A and 64 in arm B. The median 16-week PFS rates in arm A and arm B were 59% and 78%, respectively; the median PFS times were 22.3 weeks and 39.6 weeks, respectively. Stable disease >24 weeks was observed 6 and 8 patients in Arms A and B, respectively. The ORR and CBR were 24% (all PRs) and 33% compared to 56% (one of which was a CR) and 69% in the two respective arms.

Accumulated clinical data indicate that diarrhea is the most frequently occurring toxicity associated with neratinib therapy. Although nearly all patients develop this adverse effect, up to 25% of the patients may have grade >3 diarrhea. Interestingly, while this toxic reaction usually occurs early (median onset of 3 days) in patients treated with single agent neratinib, the frequency and severity of this toxicity appears to decrease with increasing duration of therapy [46]. Neratinib-induced diarrhea can be managed with standard supportive therapy; in some instances dose interruptions and/or reductions may have to be implemented. The low incidence of cardiac toxicity suggests that small molecule inhibitors of the HER2 tyrosine kinase may be relatively safer than antibodies. Nevertheless, the cardiac safety profile for neratinib must be regarded as preliminary.

Afatinib

Still in early phase clinical trials, afatinib, an irreversible kinase inhibitor of HER1 and HER2, also appears to have the ability to (at least partially) overcome trastuzumab resistance. In a small phase 2 study involving 41 subjects with HER2-positive breast cancers progressing on trastuzumab, objective response (OR), all partial responses, was observed in four patients [48]. The median PFS was approximately 100 days. Even though the reported clinical benefit rate (i.e., OR + SD) was 46%, some of the patients may not have had stable disease of >24 weeks, a duration used in numerous other studies of HER2-targeted agents. What is also uncertain is how many of the 19 subjects who achieved clinical benefit from afatinib were among the 68% of those who previously responded to trastuzumab. Equally important, grade 1 or 2 treatment-related AEs occurred in almost every subject, with diarrhea and asthenia being reported most frequently. The afatinib data appear to be similar to that of neratinib and lapatinib in that dual targeting of HER1 and HER2 may overcome some of the resistance induced by increased expression of other HER family members or reprogrammed receptor-mediated signaling [49].

HER2/neu/HER3

The robustness of signaling through HER2 heterodimers is perhaps most intriguingly demonstrated by two notable findings. First, at least 10 EGF (epidermal growth factor)-like molecules have been shown to bind EGFR, HER3 and HER4; none, however, binds to HER2 [50]. The reason why identification of a stimulating ligand remains elusive could be related to HER2 itself. Analysis of the crystal structure exposed a pair of clarifying facets

about the receptor: a) the extended conformation of monomeric HER2 may hinder binding of any EGF-like peptide as well as trastuzumab (Figure 1) [51]; and b) structural defects at the receptor binding site appear to be the result of unconserved or altered amino acid residues [14]. Second, is the surprising finding that although neither monomeric HER2 (ligand-less) nor HER3 (kinase-impaired) can support linear signaling alone, the combination appears to possess the most potent mitogenic properties [17]. Furthermore, the truncated receptor is notable for one other reason, it preferentially dimerizes with HER3. These findings provided the rationale to develop an agent that could prevent the formation of any HER2 heterodimer, but perhaps especially one which contained HER3.

Molecularly, pertuzumab (Perjeta™, Genentech) is a humanized recombinant IgG1 monoclonal antibody that recognizes and binds to a site on the extracellular dimerization domain of HER2 (Figure 2). This notion is supported by structural evidence showing that contact between extracellular domains I and III (i.e., the principal HER ligand-binding site) produces an "extended conformation" of the receptor, which limits ligand access [51]. This peculiar conformational status may also explain why HER2 is the preferential dimeric partner for all other family members [15]. Although both pertuzumab and trastuzumab are monoclonal antibodies that inhibit HER2-mediated signaling, a number of notable differences do exist. First, each agent recognizes discrete extracellular epitopes, [52] a finding that could have important therapeutic ramifications. Second, the unique binding site of pertuzumab induces structural aberrations that sterically prevent the process of homo- and hetero-dimerization. In effect, pertuzumab could inhibit HER2 signaling initiated by ligand-activated HER1 or HER3 and thus provide even greater inhibition of HER2 than trastuzumab [53]. Notably, the Fab fragment of pertuzumab appears to be just as effective as the intact antibody in blocking HER2 signaling [54]. This finding means that the inhibitory effect may not be mediated solely by an antibody-dependent cell-mediated cytotoxicity mechanism.

Based on their unique binding sites, as well as preclinical data showing enhanced activity with combined antibody therapy, [55] a phase II clinical trial was performed to assess the effectiveness of the pertuzumab/trastuzumab doublet in patients with advanced HER2-positive breast cancer progressing on prior trastuzumab therapy [56]. In this single arm study, women with HER2 over-expressing metastatic breast cancer were treated with standard weekly or three-weekly doses of trastuzumab plus pertuzumab, 420 mg every 21 days following an 840 mg loading dose. The primary endpoints were RR and CBR. The first eight cycles constituted the main treatment period with tumor assessment occurring prior to cycles 3, 5, and 7. For those who were treated further, response status was evaluated every three months thereafter. Treatment was continued until disease progression or unacceptable

toxicity. The most important secondary endpoint was safety, especially cardiac events. Despite the relatively long median duration of prior trastuzumab therapy (i.e., 16.2 months) among the 66 patients enrolled in the study, the ORR was 24.2% (5 CRs and 11 PRs); the CBR was 50%. Of note, some patients exhibited delayed tumor responses as several patients with SD eventually achieved an objective response. Furthermore, clinical benefit appeared to be quite durable with median PFS of approximately 5½ months. Because of the purported regulatory role of HER2 in the development of cardiac myocytes, myocardial function was evaluated after cycles 1, 2, 4, 6, and 8. Based on predetermined criteria, three patients had evidence of cardiac dysfunction although none were symptomatic. Left ventricular ejection function returned to normal in two patients, even though cancer therapy was not interrupted. The third patient withdrew from the study because of disease progression. Overall, the mean LVEF remained stable during the first eight cycles. The most frequently reported adverse effect was diarrhea which occurred in 64% of the patients; however, this toxic reaction was classified as grade >3 in only two patients.

The question regarding the potential applicability of pertuzumab in breast tumors with low level expression of HER2 (i.e., 1+ or 2+ by IHC) appears to have been answered by the results of a phase II clinical trial that were recently reported [57]. Restricted to patients with advanced “HER2-negative” breast cancer, patients were randomly assigned to receive pertuzumab, either 420 mg (following an 840 mg loading dose, Arm A) or 1,050 mg (Arm B) every three weeks. Of the 78 evaluable patients only two achieved a PR, while four others had SD >24 weeks as their best outcomes. Hence, these data do not support the notion that pertuzumab would be active in breast tumors that do not over-express HER2.

Results of the NeoSphere trial, a phase 2 neoadjuvant study of pertuzumab involving 417 patients have been published [58]. Designed as a four-arm study, three of which contained pertuzumab in combination with trastuzumab or docetaxel or all three agents compared to the trastuzumab/docetaxel doublet, eligibility was restricted to treatment-naïve patients with locally advanced HER2-positive breast cancer. Pathological CR was significantly greater among women randomized to the regimen containing pertuzumab, trastuzumab, and docetaxel (45.8%) compared to the trastuzumab plus docetaxel (29%), pertuzumab plus docetaxel (24), and pertuzumab plus trastuzumab (16.8%) arms. Of note, the incidence of serious AEs was similar among all groups receiving docetaxel, but lower in the arm containing only the two antibodies.

The results of a double-blind, randomized, placebo-controlled phase III clinical trial (CLEOPATRA) were recently published (study details in Table 1) [59]. The acronym, CLEOPATRA, is derived from CLinical Evaluation Of Pertuzumab And TRAstuzumab. This study involved 808 patients

with HER2-positive metastatic breast cancer who were randomized to receive the combination of trastuzumab plus docetaxel with (experimental arm) or without (control arm) pertuzumab until disease progression or the development of toxicity that could not be effectively managed. The primary end point was an independent assessment of PFS. Secondary end points included OS, investigator-assessed PFS, RR, and safety. The median PFS in the control and experimental arms were 12.4 months and 18.5 months, respectively (HR, 0.62%; 95% CI, 0.51 to 0.75; $p < 0.001$); interim analysis of OS indicated a trend in favor of the pertuzumab-containing regimen. The safety profile was generally similar in the two groups, with no increase in left ventricular systolic dysfunction. However, the rates of grade >3 febrile neutropenia and diarrhea were higher in the pertuzumab group compared to the control group.

Based on these findings, the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) approved pertuzumab in June of 2012 for clinical use in combination with trastuzumab and docetaxel for treatment-naïve patients with HER2-positive metastatic breast cancer.

HER2/neu

Ado-trastuzumab emtansine

One of the most significant limitations of cytotoxic chemotherapy is the lack of tumor selectivity. As such, chemotherapy doses have traditionally been determined by what is deemed to be “tolerable” toxicity to normal cells. Coupling target specificity with the observation that trastuzumab’s modest anti-tumor effect was substantially improved by the addition of chemotherapy led to the idea that antibodies could be used to deliver chemotherapy rather selectively to tumor cells. However, the efficacy of antibody-chemotherapy (drug) conjugates (ADCs) has historically been limited by variable expression of the target antigen, defective tumor cell uptake mechanisms, and unreliable linkers used in the conjugation process.

A novel therapeutic entity known as trastuzumab-DM1 (T-DM1, ado-trastuzumab emtansine, Kadcyla, Genentech) has been developed that appears to have resolved all of the above issues (Figure 2). For example, maytansine, [60] a natural product derived from the Ethiopian shrub *Maytenus serrata*, is a potent anti-microtubule agent [61]. However, significant neurological and gastrointestinal toxicities observed in clinical trials of the agent precluded further testing in humans [62]. In order to improve the therapeutic index, it was hypothesized that targeted delivery of maytansine could reduce, or even prevent, some drug-associated toxicities. Because HER2 is over-expressed in approximately 20% of breast cancers, trastuzumab was identified as a reasonable vehicle for drug delivery. To achieve this, a maytansine derivative (i.e., emtansine, DM1) was synthesized. The resulting maytansinoid was configured to have an easily cleavable methyl disulfide “handle” linked to trastuzumab [63]. Notable also, DM1 was shown to be up to 10-fold more potent than the parent

compound. Hence, T-DM1 has the potential not only of retaining the anti-tumor properties of the individual agents but also maintaining a tolerable side effect profile.

Investigators of a dose-finding phase I study reported dose-limiting thrombocytopenia occurred at 4.8 mg/kg (given every three weeks) [64]. Platelet nadirs were observed approximately a week after drug administration with recovery occurring seven days later. None of the patients had clinically significant bleeding. No other grade 4 adverse event and no cardiac-specific toxicity have been observed. Other frequently occurring side effects included liver function test abnormalities, fatigue, nausea and anemia. However, none of these adverse events were greater than grade 2. Although not an efficacy study, the clinical benefit rate, which included five objective responses, was 73% among 15 patients treated at 3.6 mg/kg, the maximum tolerated dose.

Two phase 2 studies have been conducted in women with HER2-positive metastatic breast cancer progressing on previous HER2-therapy and chemotherapy. All patients were treated with T-DM1 at a dose of 3.6 mg/kg once every three weeks. Even though the median follow-up period of the first study was approximately four months, image-confirmed objective responses (CRs and PRs) were achieved in 29 of 108 evaluable patients; the median PFS was 4.6 months. Notably, 24% of 66 subjects who received prior therapy with both trastuzumab and lapatinib achieved an objective response [65]. Results of another phase 2 study were recently published [66]. The study included 110 patients, 109 of who had received prior anthracycline, taxane, capecitabine, trastuzumab and lapatinib, with disease progressing on the last treatment regimen. The median duration of prior trastuzumab therapy for metastatic disease was 19.4 months; and 6.9 months for lapatinib. The primary endpoint was ORR assessed by independent review. Median follow-up was 8.3 months (range 0.7–13.1). Thirty-six (32.7%) of the enrolled patients achieved a PR as their best tumor outcome; disease stabilization occurred in 51 additional patients; the CBR was 44.5%. The major reason for discontinuation of therapy was disease progression.

The most encouraging results emanated from a phase 3 clinical trial known as EMILIA which compared T-DM1 against the combination of lapatinib plus capecitabine as second-line therapy for patients with HER2-positive breast cancer progressing on trastuzumab and a taxane (study details in Table 1) [67]. T-DM1 was given at 3.6 mg/kg once every three weeks or capecitabine, 1000 mg/m² twice daily for 14 days every three weeks plus lapatinib, 1,250 mg daily until disease progression or unmanageable toxicity. Primary end points were PFS (by independent review), OS and tolerability. A total of 991 patients were enrolled, 978 of who received assigned treatment. Median duration of follow-up was approximately one year. Compared to the capecitabine/lapatinib, T-DM1 reduced the risk of disease progression or death by 35% (6.4 mo vs

9.6 mo; HR, 0.65 [95% CI, 0.55 to 0.77]; $p < 0.001$). Median OS at the second interim analysis crossed the pre-specified efficacy stopping boundary (30.9 mo vs. 25.1 mo; HR, 0.68 [95% CI, 0.55 to 0.85; $p < 0.001$). The ORR was higher with T-DM1 compared to the lapatinib/capecitabine doublet (43.6%, vs. 30.8%; $p < 0.001$). The most common grade >3 AEs which were higher in the T-DM1 arm included thrombocytopenia (12.9% vs 0.2%), increased AST (2.9% vs 1.4%), and increased ALT (4.3% vs 0.8%) while diarrhea (20.7% vs 1.6%), hand-foot syndrome (16.4% vs 0%) and vomiting (4.5% vs 0.8%) occurred more frequently in those receiving capecitabine/lapatinib.

Neu uncertainties

In spite of all the accumulated information, the clarity of a number of important aspects linking the therapeutic agents with the receptor still remains ill-defined. For instance, an area of intense inquiry involves the precise mechanisms of trastuzumab's anti-tumor effect. As such, a number of hypotheses have been proposed. One involves perturbation of critical signal transduction pathways following receptor internalization and subsequent proteolysis. As such, signaling through key molecules located "downstream" of the receptor, including phosphatidylinositol 3 kinase (PI3K) and mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK), is disrupted (Figure 2).[68,69] In addition to the observed effects on tumor proliferation, the antibody may also impact cell survival pathways such as angiogenesis by modulating the release of pro-angiogenic and anti-angiogenic factors [70,71]. The corollary to the latter two notions is that activating mutations of regulatory proteins such as PI3K or MAPK could mediate intrinsic resistance to any anti-HER2 therapy, which would lead to tumor growth, inhibition of apoptosis, and angiogenesis.

Tumor cells treated with trastuzumab also exhibit growth arrest in G₁ phase which appears to be due to reduced concentrations of proteins involved in the separation of p27^{kip1} and the cyclin E/cdk2 complex [72]. Two other anti-tumor mechanisms include inhibition of DNA repair, an effect partially mediated by modulating p21^{WAF1} and decreased formation of the constitutively active truncated form of HER2 by blocking proteolytic cleavage of the ECD [73,74]. Furthermore, because HER2 can be recycled to the cell membrane in its functional state, part of trastuzumab's anti-tumor mechanism may involve recruitment of a protein known as c-Cbl which enhances lysosomal-enhanced degradation of the receptor [75]. Nonetheless, controversy exists regarding these proposed mechanisms. Some investigators contend that cell surface receptor down-regulation is not an important anti-tumor mechanism of trastuzumab [75,76] as they demonstrate that the antibody does not alter any of the previous findings, even the ability to cause apoptosis as the terminal event [77]. An alternative, though not necessarily mutually exclusive, explanation

of the function of trastuzumab involves the recruitment of an immune component. Suggestive, though not absolute, evidence indicate that the antibody binds and activates Fc receptors expressed on immunocompetent lymphocytes and NK cells resulting in antibody dependent cellular cytotoxicity (ADCC) [78]. However, even the phenomenon of ADCC may not be important as inhibition of tumor growth has been observed with antibodies that lack the Fc fragment [54]. What is absolutely certain is that mere binding of trastuzumab to the receptor alone provides only a superficial explanation of how the antibody elicits its effect.

Another nuance relates to the relative importance of HER1 and HER3 in the disease. Although high level HER1 expression has been found in breast cancer, specific anti-HER1 blockade has not translated into anti-tumor efficacy [79]. However, circumstantial evidence related to the efficacy of lapatinib, neratinib, and afatinib suggests a reprogrammable melding of HER1 into the HER2 signaling pathway [80]. Equally intriguing is a finding related to HER3 and the androgen receptor (AR). Although the role of androgens (compared to estrogens) in breast cancer growth and disease progression is less well understood, high level expression of the AR has been found in HER2-positive/ER-negative breast tumor samples [81]. What makes this finding particularly alluring relates to the gene expression profile, one aspect of which indicated ligand-dependent AR-mediated signaling up-regulated *WNT7B* (a portmanteau of Wg [wingless] in *Drosophila* and INT 1 [the mammalian homologue of Wg]) transcription and activated β -catenin [82]. Through their collaborative effort, AR and β -catenin have been directly linked to androgen-induced HER3 expression; and indirectly, to the pernicious tumor characteristics imparted by the HER2/HER3 heterodimer [83].

Finally, it remains uncertain whether the pathologic alterations of the receptor occur very early (i.e., atypical hyperplasia) in the tumorigenic process. The determination of when this functional abnormality occurs may be crucial as earlier detection (and treatment) may improve the prognosis of a significant number of patients.

Neu conclusion

Despite the approval of lapatinib, pertuzumab, and ado-trastuzumab emtansine, their current use is limited primarily to patients with metastatic disease. Because the latter two agents have only recently been approved and lapatinib has been shown to be inferior to trastuzumab, their restricted clinical applicability is not surprising. However, it should also be noted that since 2007, the St. Gallen expert consensus continues to support the use of adjuvant trastuzumab in patients with early HER2-positive breast cancer. The same recommendation can be seen in the National Comprehensive Cancer Network (NCCN) guidelines (version 2.2013). What will likely happen in the near future is to determine the efficacy of ado-trastuzumab emtansine in the adjuvant setting. In addition, the approval of pertuzumab

in combination with trastuzumab and docetaxel as first-line therapy for metastatic disease may also translate into moving the triple-drug regimen into patients with early disease. Both new agents will be at least non-inferior, and possibly even superior, to trastuzumab. The real conundrum will be whether either agent should supersede trastuzumab (alone) as first-line adjuvant HER2 therapy. In addition, even though pertuzumab is most effective when given in combination with trastuzumab, it would be irrational to conduct a clinical trial involving both agents in patients with breast cancers that do not overexpress HER2.

One dilemma that frequently arises with the introduction of effective new drugs is that while expanded hope can be offered to patients with this subtype of breast cancer, the situation, paradoxically, creates a sequencing quandary. Nonetheless, a reasonable sequence for advanced disease is use the combination of pertuzumab, trastuzumab and docetaxel or trastuzumab-DM1 as first-line therapy, followed by the regimen not selected initially, then follow with lapatinib plus capecitabine or dual anti-HER therapy without chemotherapy. In the adjuvant setting, trastuzumab remains the anti-HER2 agent of choice until results of contemplated clinical trials are known.

While scientifically rational, targeting tumor angiogenesis has only achieved modest success in oncology. Recent results reported at the 2013 San Antonio Breast Cancer Symposium indicated that the addition of adjuvant bevacizumab to trastuzumab therapy failed to improve invasive disease-free survival in patients with HER2-positive breast cancer. Although numerous other targets such as mTOR (mammalian target of rapamycin), PI3K, HSP (heat-shock protein) 90, and IGF1R (insulin-like growth factor receptor) 1 have been identified, one that may carry as much importance is the AR. The preliminary findings alluded to previously suggest that verifying the presence of AR in HER2-positive breast tumors may not only be reasonable but targeting both receptors may also be therapeutically rational.

Finally, it is somewhat perplexing that when the considerable knowledge gained is coupled with the substantial progress made, especially with regards to targeting HER2, there are still perceptibly large gaps in our understanding of the receptor. More than likely, some of the current voids will be filled in the not too distant future. As such, *neu* concepts should continue to improve the therapeutic management of patients with HER2-positive breast cancer.

Competing Interests

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

References

1. Schechter AL, Stern DF, Vaidyanathan L, Decker SJ, Drebin JA, *et al.* (1984). The neu oncogene: an erb-B-related gene encoding a 185,000-Mr tumour antigen. *Nature*, 312: 513-516.
2. Vennström B, Bishop JM (1982). Isolation and characterization of chicken DNA homologous to the two putative oncogenes of avian erythroblastosis virus. *Cell*, 28: 135-143.

3. van der Geer P, Hunter T, Lindberg RA. (1994). Receptor protein-tyrosine kinases and their signal transduction pathways. *Annu Rev Cell Biol*, 10:251-337..
4. Zhang X, Gureasko J, Shen K, Cole PA, Kuriyan J (2006). An allosteric mechanism for activation of the kinase domain of epidermal growth factor receptor. *Cell*, 125: 1137-1149.
5. Hynes NE, Stern DF (1994). The biology of erbB-2/neu/HER-2 and its role in cancer. *Biochim Biophys Acta*, 1198: 165-184.
6. McCann AH, Dervan PA, O'Regan M, Codd MB, Gullick WJ, et al. (1991). Prognostic significance of c-erbB-2 and estrogen receptor status in human breast cancer. *Cancer Res*, 51: 3296-3303.
7. Ménard S, Fortis S, Castiglioni F, Agresti R, Balsari A (2001). HER2 as a prognostic factor in breast cancer. *Oncology*, 61 Suppl 2: 67-72.
8. Wolff AC, Hammond ME, Schwartz JN, Hagerty KL, Allred DC, et al. (2007). American Society of Clinical Oncology/College of American Pathologists guideline recommendations for human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 testing in breast cancer. *J Clin Oncol*, 25: 118-145.
9. Slamon DJ, Leyland-Jones B, Shak S, Fuchs H, Paton V, et al. (2001). Use of chemotherapy plus a monoclonal antibody against HER2 for metastatic breast cancer that overexpresses HER2. *N Engl J Med*, 344: 783-792.
10. von Minckwitz G, du Bois A, Schmidt M, Maass N, Cufer T, et al. (2009). Trastuzumab beyond progression in human epidermal growth factor receptor 2-positive advanced breast cancer: a german breast group 26/breast international group 03-05 study. *J Clin Oncol*, 27: 1999-2006.
11. Montemurro F, Donadio M, Clavarezza M, Redana S, Jacomuzzi ME, Valabrega G, et al. (2006). Outcome of patients with HER2-positive advanced breast cancer progressing during trastuzumab-based therapy. *Oncologist*, 11:318-324..
12. Romond EH, Perez EA, Bryant J, Suman VJ, Geyer CE Jr, et al. (2005). Trastuzumab plus adjuvant chemotherapy for operable HER2-positive breast cancer. *N Engl J Med*, 353: 1673-1684.
13. Piccart-Gebhart MJ, Procter M, Leyland-Jones B, Goldhirsch A, Untch M, et al. (2005). Trastuzumab after adjuvant chemotherapy in HER2-positive breast cancer. *N Engl J Med*, 353: 1659-1672.
14. Di Fiore PP, Pierce JH, Kraus MH, Segatto O, King CR, et al. (1987). erbB-2 is a potent oncogene when overexpressed in NIH/3T3 cells. *Science*, 237: 178-182.
15. Graus-Porta D, Beerli RR, Daly JM, Hynes NE (1997). ErbB-2, the preferred heterodimerization partner of all ErbB receptors, is a mediator of lateral signaling. *EMBO J*, 16: 1647-1655.
16. Olayioye MA, Graus-Porta D, Beerli RR, Rohrer J, Gay B, et al. (1998). ErbB-1 and ErbB-2 acquire distinct signaling properties dependent upon their dimerization partner. *Mol Cell Biol*, 18: 5042-5051.
17. Alimandi M, Romano A, Curia MC, Muraro R, Fedi P, et al. (1995). Cooperative signaling of ErbB3 and ErbB2 in neoplastic transformation and human mammary carcinomas. *Oncogene*, 10: 1813-1821.
18. Kokai Y, Myers JN, Wada T, Brown VI, LeVea CM, et al. (1989). Synergistic interaction of p185-neu and the EGF receptor leads to transformation of rodent fibroblasts. *Cell*, 58: 287-292.
19. Segatto O, King CR, Pierce JH, Di Fiore PP, Aaronson SA (1988). Different structural alterations upregulate in vitro tyrosine kinase activity and transforming potency of the erbB-2 gene. *Mol Cell Biol*, 8: 5570-5574.
20. Xia W, Liu L-H, Ho P, Spector NL. (2004). Truncated ErbB2 receptor (p95ErbB2) is regulated by heregulin through heterodimer formation with ErbB3 yet remains sensitive to the dual EGFR/ErbB2 kinase inhibitor GW72016. *Oncogene*, 23:646-653.
21. Molina MA, Sáez R, Ramsey EE, Garcia-Barchino MJ, Rojo F, et al. (2002). NH(2)-terminal truncated HER-2 protein but not full-length receptor is associated with nodal metastasis in human breast cancer. *Clin Cancer Res*, 8: 347-353.
22. Wood ER, Truesdale AT, McDonald OB, Yuan D, Hassell A, Dickerson SH, et al. (2004). A unique structure for epidermal growth factor receptor bound to GW572016 (Lapatinib): relationships among protein conformation, inhibitor off-rate, and receptor activity in tumor cells. *Cancer Res*, 64:6652-6659..
23. Burris HA III, Hurwitz H, Dees EC, Dowlati A, Blackwell KL, O'Neil B, et al. (2005). Phase I study, pharmacokinetics, and clinical activity study of lapatinib (GW572016), a reversible dual inhibitor of epidermal growth factor receptor tyrosine kinases, in heavily pretreated patients with metastatic carcinomas. *J Clin Oncol*, 23:5305-5313.
24. Burris HA 3rd (2004). Dual kinase inhibition in the treatment of breast cancer: initial experience with the EGFR/ErbB-2 inhibitor lapatinib. *Oncologist*, 9 Suppl 3: 10-15.
25. Geyer CE, Forster J, Lindquist D, Chan S, Romieu CG, et al. (2006). Lapatinib plus capecitabine for HER2-positive advanced breast cancer. *N Engl J Med*, 355: 2733-2743.
26. Cameron D, Casey M, Press M, Lindquist D, Pienkowski T, Romieu CG, et al. (2008). A phase III randomized comparison of lapatinib plus capecitabine versus capecitabine alone in women with advanced breast cancer that has progressed on trastuzumab: updated efficacy and biomarker analyses. *Breast Cancer Res Treat*, 112:533-543.
27. Sonpavde G (2007). Lapatinib plus capecitabine in breast cancer. *N Engl J Med*, 356: 1471.
28. Geyer CE, Forster J, Cameron MD. (2007). Lapatinib plus capecitabine in breast cancer. *N Engl J Med*, 356:1471-1472.
29. DiStefano A, Yong Yap Y, Hortobagyi GN, Blumenschein GR (1979). The natural history of breast cancer patients with brain metastases. *Cancer*, 44: 1913-1918.
30. Clayton AJ, Danson S, Jolly S, Ryder WD, Burt PA, et al. (2004). Incidence of cerebral metastases in patients treated with trastuzumab for metastatic breast cancer. *Br J Cancer*, 91: 639-643.
31. Bendell JC, Domchek SM, Burstein HJ, Harris L, Younger J, et al. (2003). Central nervous system metastases in women who receive trastuzumab-based therapy for metastatic breast carcinoma. *Cancer*, 97: 2972-2977.
32. Lin NU, Diéras V, Paul D, Lossignol D, Christodoulou C, et al. (2009). Multicenter phase II study of lapatinib in patients with brain metastases from HER2-positive breast cancer. *Clin Cancer Res*, 15: 1452-1459.
33. Gomez HL, Doval DC, Chavez MA, Ang PC, Aziz Z, et al. (2008). Efficacy and safety of lapatinib as first-line therapy for ErbB2-amplified locally advanced or metastatic breast cancer. *J Clin Oncol*, 26: 2999-3005.
34. Johnston S, Pippin J Jr, Pivot X, Lichinitser M, Sadeghi S, et al. (2009). Lapatinib combined with letrozole versus letrozole and placebo as first-line therapy for postmenopausal hormone receptor-positive metastatic breast cancer. *J Clin Oncol*, 27: 5538-5546.
35. Shou J, Massarweh S, Osborne CK, Wakeling AE, Ali S, et al. (2004). Mechanisms of tamoxifen resistance: increased estrogen receptor-HER2/neu cross-talk in ER/HER2-positive breast cancer. *J Natl Cancer Inst*, 96: 926-935.
36. Blackwell KL, Burstein HJ, Storniolo AM, Rugo H, Sledge G, et al. (2004). Randomized study of Lapatinib alone or in combination with trastuzumab in women with ErbB2-positive, trastuzumab-refractory metastatic breast cancer. *J Clin Oncol*, 28: 1124-1130.
37. Perez EA, Koehler M, Byrne J, Preston AJ, Rappold E, et al. (2008). Cardiac safety of lapatinib: pooled analysis of 3689 patients enrolled in clinical trials. *Mayo Clin Proc*, 83: 679-686.
38. Kannel WB (2000). Incidence and epidemiology of heart failure. *Heart Fail Rev*, 5: 167-173.
39. (Aug 20, 2013). Accessed at <http://clinicaltrials.gov/show/NCT00490139>, .
40. Baselga J, Bradbury I, Eidtmann H, Di Cosimo S, de Azambuja E, et al. (2012). Lapatinib with trastuzumab for HER2-positive early breast cancer (NeoALTTO): a randomised, open-label, multicentre, phase 3 trial. *Lancet*, 379: 633-640.
41. Rabin dran SK, Discafani CM, Rosfjord EC, Baxter M, Floyd MB, et al. (2004). Antitumor activity of HKI-272, an orally active, irreversible inhibitor of the HER-2 tyrosine kinase. *Cancer Res*, 64: 3958-3965.
42. Mather B, Viswanathan K, Miller K, Long T. (2006). Michael addition reactions in macromolecular design for emerging technologies. *Progress Polymer Science*, 31:487-531.
43. Yun CH, Mengwasser KE, Toms AV, Woo MS, Greulich H, et al. (2008). The T790M mutation in EGFR kinase causes drug resistance by increasing the affinity for ATP. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A*, 105: 2070-2075.
44. Wong KK, Fracasso PM, Bukowski RM, Lynch TJ, Munster PN, et al. (2009). A phase I study with neratinib (HKI-272), an irreversible pan ErbB receptor tyrosine kinase inhibitor, in patients with solid tumors. *Clin Cancer Res*, 15: 2552-2558.
45. Chow L, Jiang Z, Epstein R, Bondarenko I, Awada A, Coughlin C, et al. (2009). Safety and efficacy of neratinib (HKI-272) in combination with paclitaxel in patients with solid tumors. *J Clin Oncol*, 27 (15S): abstract 3557.
46. Awada A, Dirix L, Manso Sanchez L, Xu B, Luu T, et al. (2013). Safety and efficacy of neratinib (HKI-272) plus vinorelbine in the treatment of patients with ErbB2-positive metastatic breast cancer pretreated with anti-HER2 therapy. *Ann Oncol*, 24: 109-116.
47. Burstein HJ, Sun Y, Dirix LY, Jiang Z, Paridaens R, et al. (2010). Neratinib, an irreversible ErbB receptor tyrosine kinase inhibitor, in patients with advanced ErbB2-positive breast cancer. *J Clin Oncol*, 28: 1301-1307.
48. Lin NU, Winer EP, Wheatley D, Carey LA, Houston S, et al. (2012). A phase II study of afatinib (BIBW 2992), an irreversible ErbB family blocker, in patients with HER2-positive metastatic breast cancer progressing after trastuzumab. *Breast Cancer Res Treat*, 133: 1057-1065.
49. Ritter CA, Perez-Torres M, Rinehart C, Guix M, Dugger T, et al. (2007). Human breast cancer cells selected for resistance to trastuzumab in vivo overexpress epidermal growth factor receptor

- and ErbB ligands and remain dependent on the ErbB receptor network. *Clin Cancer Res*, 13: 4909-4919.
50. Mendelsohn J, Baselga J (2000). The EGF receptor family as targets for cancer therapy. *Oncogene*, 19: 6550-6565.
 51. Burgess AW, Cho HS, Eigenbrot C, Ferguson KM, Garrett TP, et al. (2003). An open-and-shut case? Recent insights into the activation of EGF/ErbB receptors. *Mol Cell*, 12: 541-552.
 52. Cho HS, Mason K, Ramyar KX, Stanley AM, Gabelli SB, et al. (2003). Structure of the extracellular region of HER2 alone and in complex with the Herceptin Fab. *Nature*, 421: 756-760.
 53. Agus DB, Akita RW, Fox WD, Lewis GD, Higgins B, et al. (2002). Targeting ligand-activated ErbB2 signaling inhibits breast and prostate tumor growth. *Cancer Cell*, 2: 127-137.
 54. Fan Z, Masui H, Altas I, Mendelsohn J (1993). Blockade of epidermal growth factor receptor function by bivalent and monovalent fragments of 225 anti-epidermal growth factor receptor monoclonal antibodies. *Cancer Res*, 53: 4322-4328.
 55. Scheuer W, Friess T, Burtscher H, Bossenmaier B, Endl J, Hasmann M. (2009). Strongly enhanced antitumor activity of trastuzumab and pertuzumab combination treatment on HER2-positive human xenograft tumor models. *Cancer Res*, 69:9330-9336.
 56. Baselga J, Gelmon KA, Verma S, Wardley A, Conte P, Miles D, et al. (2010). Phase II trial of pertuzumab and trastuzumab in patients with human epidermal growth factor receptor 2-positive metastatic breast cancer that progressed during prior trastuzumab therapy. *J Clin Oncol*, 28:1138-1144.
 57. Gianni L, Llado A, Bianchi G, Cortes J, Kellokumpu-Lehtinen PL, Cameron DA, et al. (2010). Open-label, phase II, multicenter, randomized study of the efficacy and safety of two dose levels of pertuzumab, a human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 dimerization inhibitor, in patients with human epidermal growth factor receptor 2-negative metastatic breast cancer. *J Clin Oncol*, 28:1131-1137.
 58. Gianni L, Pienkowski T, Im YH, Roman L, Tseng LM, et al. (2012). Efficacy and safety of neoadjuvant pertuzumab and trastuzumab in women with locally advanced, inflammatory, or early HER2-positive breast cancer (NeoSphere): a randomised multicentre, open-label, phase 2 trial. *Lancet Oncol*, 13: 25-32.
 59. Baselga J, Cortés J, Kim SB, Im SA, Hegg R, et al. (2012). Pertuzumab plus trastuzumab plus docetaxel for metastatic breast cancer. *N Engl J Med*, 366: 109-119.
 60. Remillard S, Rebhun LI, Howie GA, Kupchan SM (1975). Antimitotic activity of the potent tumor inhibitor maytansine. *Science*, 189: 1002-1005.
 61. Bhattacharyya B, Wolff J (1977). Maytansine binding to the vinblastine sites of tubulin. *FEBS Lett*, 75: 159-162.
 62. Eagan RT, Ingle JN, Rubin J, Frytak S, Moertel CG (1978). Early clinical study of an intermittent schedule for maytansine (NSC-153858): brief communication. *J Natl Cancer Inst*, 60: 93-96.
 63. Chari RV, Martell BA, Gross JL, Cook SB, Shah SA, et al. (1992). Immunoconjugates containing novel maytansinoids: promising anticancer drugs. *Cancer Res*, 52: 127-131.
 64. Krop IE, Beeram M, Modi S, Jones SF, Holden SN, Yu W, et al. (2010). Phase I study of trastuzumab-DM1, an HER2 antibody-drug conjugate, given every 3 weeks to patients with HER2-positive metastatic breast cancer. *J Clin Oncol*, 28:2698-2704.
 65. Burris HA 3rd, Rugo HS, Vukelja SJ, Vogel CL, Borson RA, et al. (2011). Phase II study of the antibody drug conjugate trastuzumab-DM1 for the treatment of human epidermal growth factor receptor 2 (HER2)-positive breast cancer after prior HER2-directed therapy. *J Clin Oncol*, 29: 398-405.
 66. Krop IE, LoRusso P, Miller KD, Modi S, Yardley D, Rodriguez G, et al. (2012). A phase II study of trastuzumab emtansine in patients with human epidermal growth factor receptor 2-positive metastatic breast cancer who were previously treated with trastuzumab, lapatinib, an anthracycline, a taxane, and capecitabine. *J Clin Oncol*, 30:3234-3241.
 67. Verma S, Miles D, Gianni L, Krop IE, Welslau M, et al. (2012). Trastuzumab emtansine for HER2-positive advanced breast cancer. *N Engl J Med*, 367: 1783-1791.
 68. Yakes FM, Chinratanalab W, Ritter CA, King W, Seelig S, et al. (2002). Herceptin-induced inhibition of phosphatidylinositol-3 kinase and Akt is required for antibody-mediated effects on p27, cyclin D1, and antitumor action. *Cancer Res*, 62: 4132-4141.
 69. Wang CX, Koay DC, Edwards A, Lu Z, Mor G, et al. (2005). In vitro and in vivo effects of combination of Trastuzumab (Herceptin) and Tamoxifen in breast cancer. *Breast Cancer Res Treat*, 92: 251-263.
 70. Petit AM, Rak J, Hung MC, et al. (1997). Neutralizing antibodies against epidermal growth factor and ErbB-2/neu receptor tyrosine kinases down-regulate vascular endothelial growth factor production by tumor cells in vitro and in vivo: angiogenic implications for signal transduction therapy of solid tumors. *Am J Pathol*, 151(6):1523-1530.
 71. Izumi Y, Xu L, di Tomaso E, Fukumura D, Jain RK (2002). Tumor biology: herceptin acts as an anti-angiogenic cocktail. *Nature*, 416: 279-280.
 72. Lane HA, Beuvink I, Motoyama AB, Daly JM, Neve RM, et al. (2000). ErbB2 potentiates breast tumor proliferation through modulation of p27(Kip1)-Cdk2 complex formation: receptor overexpression does not determine growth dependency. *Mol Cell Biol*, 20: 3210-3223.
 73. Molina MA, Sáez R, Ramsey EE, Garcia-Barchino MJ, Rojo F, et al. (2002). NH(2)-terminal truncated HER-2 protein but not full-length receptor is associated with nodal metastasis in human breast cancer. *Clin Cancer Res*, 8: 347-353.
 74. Pietras RJ, Pegram MD, Finn RS, Maneval DA, Slamon DJ (1998). Remission of human breast cancer xenografts on therapy with humanized monoclonal antibody to HER-2 receptor and DNA-reactive drugs. *Oncogene*, 17: 2235-2249.
 75. Yeon CH, Pegram MD (2005). Anti-erbB-2 antibody trastuzumab in the treatment of HER2-amplified breast cancer. *Invest New Drugs*, 23: 391-409.
 76. Austin CD, De Maziere AM, Pisacane PI, van Dijk SM, Eigenbrot C, Sliwkowski MX, et al. (2004). Endocytosis and sorting of ErbB2 and the site of action of cancer therapeutics trastuzumab and geldanamycin. *Mol Biol Cell*, 15:5268-5282.
 77. Gennari R, Menard S, Fagnoni F, Ponchio L, Scelsi M, Tagliabue E, et al. (2004). Pilot study of the mechanism of action of preoperative trastuzumab in patients with primary operable breast tumors overexpressing HER2. *Clin Cancer Res*, 10:5650-5655.
 78. Clynes RA, Towers TL, Presta LG, Ravetch JV. (2000). Inhibitory Fc receptors modulate in vivo cytotoxicity against tumor targets. *Nat Med*, 6:443-446.
 79. Baselga J, Albanell J, Ruiz A, Lluch A, Gascón P, et al. (2005). Phase II and tumor pharmacodynamic study of gefitinib in patients with advanced breast cancer. *J Clin Oncol*, 23: 5323-5333.
 80. Narayan M, Wilken JA, Harris LN, Baron AT, Kimbler KD, et al. (2009). Trastuzumab-induced HER reprogramming in "resistant" breast carcinoma cells. *Cancer Res*, 69: 2191-2194.
 81. Ni M, Chen Y, Lim E, Wimberly H, Bailey ST, et al. (2011). Targeting androgen receptor in estrogen receptor-negative breast cancer. *Cancer Cell*, 20: 119-131.
 82. Klaus A, Birchmeier W (2008). Wnt signalling and its impact on development and cancer. *Nat Rev Cancer*, 8: 387-398.
 83. Lee-Hoeflich ST, Crocker L, Yao E, Pham T, Munroe X, et al. (2008). A central role for HER3 in HER2-amplified breast cancer: implications for targeted therapy. *Cancer Res*, 68: 5878-5887.